

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R7.4 Applicability matrix of monitoring methods at Zar-3

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1 INTRODUCTION

The main objective of CO₂-SPICER project result R7.4 is to assess the applicability of various methods and techniques for monitoring of CO₂ storage at the Zar-3 site. The assessment covers methodology for all monitoring purposes and monitoring stages set out by valid legislation and regulations, especially by the Czech Act No. 85/2012 Sb. on the storage of carbon dioxide in natural underground geological formations.

The work was performed within project Task T7.1 "Methods and data" by Task leader CGS, assisted by MND. The applicability analysis of various monitoring methods was based on several information sources:

- existing international monitoring guidelines and methodological tools published by the European Commission, the Greenhouse Gas programme of the International Energy Agency (IEAGHG) and the United States Department of Energy (US DOE);
- literature review of CO₂ storage monitoring experience from existing sites where CO₂ is stored or used for enhanced oil recovery in similar lithologies to Zar-3, i.e. in carbonate rocks;
- review of novel monitoring techniques for CO₂ storage presented in literature and at international conferences in the last 3 years;
- analysis of data from the Zar-3 field exploration and production history, possibly suitable for CO₂ storage monitoring (provided by site operator MND).

Additional selection criteria were derived from the existing knowledge about the Zar-3 field.

2 LEGISLATIVE AND REGULATORY REQUIREMENTS ON MONITORING OF CO₂ STORAGE SITES

The monitoring requirements for CO₂ storage sites are set by the Article 13 of the Directive 2009/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the geological storage of carbon dioxide¹ and amending Council Directive 85/337/EEC, European Parliament and Council Directives 2000/60/EC, 2001/80/EC, 2004/35/EC, 2006/12/EC, 2008/1/EC and Regulation EC No 1013/2006 (hereinafter referred to as the EU CCS Directive) as well as Section (§) 9 of the Czech Act No. 85/2012 Sb., on the carbon dioxide storage into the natural rock structures² (hereinafter referred to as the Storage Act) that represents the transposition of the EU CCS Directive in the Czech national jurisdiction.

According to the Storage Act, Section (§) 9:

(1) The operator carries out monitoring of the injection facilities, the storage complex, and where appropriate the surrounding environment for the purpose of:

- a) *comparison between the actual behaviour of carbon dioxide and formation water in the storage site, with the behaviour assumed in the final report prepared in accordance with another legal regulation (i.e. the Geological Act No. 62/1988 Sb., as amended³),*
- b) *detecting significant irregularities,*
- c) *detecting migration of carbon dioxide,*
- d) *detecting potential leakage of carbon dioxide and its volume,*
- e) *detecting significant adverse effects on the surrounding environment, including in particular on drinking water, on human populations, or on users of the surrounding biosphere,*
- f) *assessing the effectiveness of any corrective measures,*
- g) *updating the assessment of the safety and integrity of the storage complex in the short and long term, including the assessment of whether the stored carbon dioxide will be completely and permanently contained.*

(2) The monitoring shall be based on a monitoring plan designed by the operator pursuant to the requirements laid down in the Annex to this Act.

(3) The plan shall be updated at least once every five years to take account of changes to the assessed risk of leakage, changes to the assessed risks to the environment and human health, new scientific knowledge, and improvements in best available technology. Updated plans shall be re-submitted for approval to the District Mining Authority.

(4) Monitoring pursuant to this Act does not affect the obligations to determine, report and verify the amount of greenhouse gas emissions pursuant to another legal regulation

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32009L0031>

² <https://aplikace.mvcr.cz/sbirka-zakonu/ViewFile.aspx?type=z&id=24080>

³ [https://www.mzp.cz/www/platnalegislativa.nsf/d79c09c54250df0dc1256e8900296e32/d058aefaaee5dfdc1257015003636e6/\\$FILE/z%20C3%A1kon%20C4%8D.%2062_1988%20Sb..pdf](https://www.mzp.cz/www/platnalegislativa.nsf/d79c09c54250df0dc1256e8900296e32/d058aefaaee5dfdc1257015003636e6/$FILE/z%20C3%A1kon%20C4%8D.%2062_1988%20Sb..pdf)

(i.e. Act No. 85/2012 Sb., on the conditions for trading in greenhouse gas emission allowances⁴, the Czech transposition of the EU ETS Directive).

Monitoring technologies and monitoring plan are handled by Annex II to the EU CCS Directive (Criteria for establishing and updating the monitoring plan referred to in Article 13 and for post-closure monitoring) as well as Annex to the Storage Act (Criteria for establishing and updating the plan of monitoring and for post-closure monitoring).

According to the Annex to the Storage Act:

The monitoring plan shall be established based on the risk assessment analysis carried out according to point 3 of the Annex to the Geological Act and shall be updated with the purpose of meeting the monitoring requirements laid out in Section (§) 9 using the following criteria:

I Establishing and updating the monitoring plan

1. Establishing the monitoring plan

1.1. The monitoring plan shall provide details of the monitoring to be deployed at the main stages of the project, including baseline, operational and post-closure monitoring. The following shall be specified for each phase:

- a) monitored parameters,*
- b) monitoring technology employed and justification for technology choice,*
- c) monitoring locations and spatial sampling rationale,*
- d) frequency of application and temporal sampling rationale.*

1.2. The parameters to be monitored shall be set to fulfil the purposes of monitoring. However, the plan shall in any case include continuous or intermittent monitoring of the following items:

- a) fugitive emissions of carbon dioxide at the injection facility,*
- b) carbon dioxide volumetric flow at injection wellheads,*
- c) carbon dioxide pressure and temperature at injection wellheads to determine mass flow,*
- d) chemical analysis of the injected material,*
- e) reservoir temperature and pressure to determine carbon dioxide phase behaviour and state.*

1.3. The choice of monitoring technology shall be based on best practice available at the time of design. The following options shall be considered and used as appropriate:

- a) technologies that can detect the presence, location and migration paths of carbon dioxide in the subsurface and at surface,*
- b) technologies that provide information about pressure-volume behaviour and areal and vertical distribution of carbon dioxide plume to refine numerical 3D simulation using the 3D model of the natural rock storage formation established pursuant to the Geological Act and its Annex,*

⁴

https://www.mzp.cz/www/platnalegislativa.nsf/29324B60A8C6D324C1256F86002E6B7D/%24file/383_201_2.pdf

- c) *technologies that can provide a wide areal spread in order to capture information on any previously undetected potential leakage pathways across the areal dimensions of the complete storage complex and beyond, in the event of significant irregularities or migration of carbon dioxide out of the storage complex.*

2. Updating the monitoring plan

The data collected from the monitoring shall be collated and interpreted. The observed results shall be compared with the behaviour predicted in dynamic simulations of the 3D pressure-volume and saturation behaviour undertaken in the context of the security characterisation pursuant to the Geological Act and its Annex (point 3).

Where there is a significant deviation between the observed and the predicted behaviour, the 3D model shall be recalibrated to reflect the observed behaviour. The recalibration shall be based on the data observations from the monitoring plan, and, where necessary to provide confidence in the recalibration assumptions, additional data shall be obtained.

Points 2 (Assessment of the planned storage complex by means of a 3D static geological model) and 3 (Characterisation of the storage dynamic behaviour, sensitivity characterisation, risk assessment) of the Annex to the Geological Act shall be repeated using the recalibrated 3D model(s) so as to generate new hazard scenarios and flux rates and to revise and update the risk assessment.

Where new sources, pathways and flux rates of carbon dioxide or observed significant deviations from previous assessments are identified as a result of history matching and model recalibration, the monitoring plan shall be updated accordingly.

II Post-closure monitoring

Post-closure monitoring shall be based on the information collected and modelled during the implementation of the monitoring plan as defined in Section (§) 9 of the Storage Act and in point 2 of the Annex to the Storage Act (on updating the monitoring plan). It shall serve in particular to provide information required for the transfer of responsibility to the competent authority as defined in Section (§) 13 of the Storage Act.

It is obvious that the Storage Act as well as the EU CCS Directive and their Annexes define parameters to be monitored directly, while monitoring technologies (methods, techniques) are defined indirectly as technologies that "...shall be based on best practice...".

To find examples of "based on best practise", we can use the Guidance Document 2 (EC 2011), one of four Guidance documents created as a part of the implementation of the EU CCS Directive. The Guidance Document 2 is focused on characterisation of the storage complex, stream composition, monitoring and corrective measures. According to its recommendations, monitoring requirements should be in principle risk-based and thus dependent on the outcome of the risk assessment and identified risks for the specific storage complex. The recommended general principles for the overall approach for monitoring and monitoring plans are:

- Monitoring is risk based, linked to identified risks from site characterisation and the overall risk assessment.
- Monitoring is specific to the storage site and complex.

- Monitoring is sufficiently extensive to cover the storage complex (including where possible the CO₂ plume), migration and behaviour of formation waters and where appropriate the surrounding environment.
- Monitoring is linked to preventive and corrective measures.
- Technology used is based on the best practice available at the time of design.
- Regular and routine reporting of monitoring data and interpretations of results takes place.
- Monitoring plans are regularly updated to take account of changes to the assessed risks to the environment and human health, new scientific knowledge, and improvements in best available technology.

The recommended main objectives and purpose of monitoring are:

- confirming containment of CO₂,
- alerting for increased leakage risk,
- identifying leakage if it occurs and significant irregularities, and
- verifying the CO₂ plume behaviour.

This can be achieved either by measuring the absence of any leakage through direct detection methods, or by verifying indirectly that the CO₂ is behaving as expected in the reservoir based on static and dynamic modelling and its updates corroborated by monitoring data. The main challenge for measuring absence of any leakage consists of spatial and temporal coverage of the monitoring method, i.e. “Where and when do we need to monitor in order to be sure that no leakage occurs”. The strategy should therefore be based on identified risks.

The parameters to be monitored as well as monitoring technologies can be divided into 4 groups (elements). The Guidance Document 2 defines the first group as *Operational*; this group shall meet the mandatory requirements, i.e. all parameters to be monitored according to point 1.2. of the Annex to the Storage Act (e.g. the CO₂ flux rate at wellhead, wellhead pressure and temperature, etc.). The continuous monitoring of parameters stated in point 1.2. is more or less known from hydrocarbon production; the "oilers" use e.g. mass flow controllers or flowmeters to measure and read the flow rates of fluids and gases, thermometers and pressure gauges to measure temperature and pressure.

Next three groups of monitoring elements and related technologies are "predefined" by point 1.3. of the Annex to the Storage Act:

Pathways - monitoring pathways for potential leakage identified by risk assessment, i.e. monitoring according to point 1.3. c) of the Annex

Plume - monitoring the plume, including tracking the injected CO₂ and its movement and water/brine behaviour, properties (pressure-volume) and movement resulting from CO₂ injection, i.e. monitoring according to point 1.3. b) of the Annex

Environmental - environmental monitoring for leakage out of the storage complex towards, at or near the surface, i.e. monitoring according to point 1.3. a) of the Annex

Examples of relevant monitoring technologies (methods, techniques) are shown in Tab. 2-1.

Tab. 2-1 Different technologies, methods and techniques suitable for monitoring, separated in groups according to the Guidance Document 2 (EC 2012).

Operational	Plume	Pathways	Environmental
<p>Injection Operations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Wellhead pressure ▪ Formation pressure and temperature ▪ Injection rate ▪ Microseismicity <p>Quantification of CO₂ injected</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mass flow ▪ Composition and phase 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Pressure and temperature ▪ Geophysics ▪ Well logging (CO₂ saturation) ▪ Surface deformation methods ▪ Tiltmeter ▪ InSAR ▪ Water properties 	<p>Wells</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Annulus pressure ▪ Corrosion ▪ Cement ▪ Logging ▪ Soil gas <p>Caprock</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Formation pressure <p>Faults & Fractures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Microseismicity ▪ Pressure interference <p>Aquifers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Water monitoring ▪ Chemistry 	<p>Leak Detection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sampling and geochemical analyses ▪ Seismic pressure interference ▪ Soil gas ▪ Vegetation stress ▪ Eddy covariance tower <p>Leak Quantification</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Soil gas ▪ Surface gas measurement <p>Impact: HSE Monitoring</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CO₂ concentration ▪ Water sampling / analysis ▪ Soils acidity ▪ Surface deformation ▪ Ecosystems surveys

Guidance Document 2 provides an overview of monitoring methods and techniques potentially suitable for each of the above-defined four groups (see Tab. 2-2). The considered methods, techniques and technologies are mostly derived from the oil and gas industry, water industry and environmental monitoring applications. They consist of both proven and developmental technologies, which are being adapted for use in geological storage of CO₂, taking account of the different fluid/gas properties and differing technical issues.

The overview is based on several earlier reviews. About 60 different methods or techniques were identified that are potentially applicable. Table 2-2 illustrates the large number and ranges of methods that should be considered, however the technologies are at varying stages of development and the list includes some technologies that have yet to be established as suitable for commercial storage projects.

Tab. 2-2 Summary of possible onshore monitoring methods and applicability according to the Guidance Document 2 (Oper. = Operational, Path's = Pathways, Env. = Environmental). Crosses mean suitable applicability.

Category	Methods / Technique	Monitoring Application			
		Oper.	Plume	Path's	Env.
Operational measurement (Wellhead and Downhole)	Wellhead Pressure and Temperature Measurement Wellhead flow metering & composition Downhole Pressure and Temperature Measurement Casing and Annulus Pressure	+			
Well Logging	Injection Well Logging (Wireline Logging) Sonic (Acoustic) Logging Cement Bond Log (Ultrasonic Well Logging) Pulsed Neutron Capture Density Logging Optical Logging Gamma Ray Logging Resistivity Log	+	+		
Well CO ₂ sampling	Well sampling & chemical analysis Tracers		+		
Seismic	2-D Seismic Survey 3D Seismic Multi-component & Timelapse Survey 4-D Seismic Array Surface Vertical Seismic Profile (VSP) Cross-Hole Seismic Survey Microseismic Survey (Passive)		+		
Shallow High resolution geophysics	Shallow 2-D Seismic High resolution acoustic imaging Ground penetrating radar			+	+
Gravity surveying	Time-lapse Gravity Well gravimetry		+		
Electrical and Electromagnetic methods	Land electrical and electromagnetic methods Induced Polarization		+		

	Spontaneous (Self) Potential Airborne EM Magnetotelluric Sounding Electromagnetic Resistivity Permanent borehole Electromagnetic (EM) Cross-hole Electromagnetic (EM) Cross-hole Electrical Resistance tomography (ERT)				
Water Sampling & Geochemistry	Ground-water Monitoring Downhole fluid chemistry Long-term borehole monitoring of pH				+
Soil/sediment sampling and Geochemistry	Soil and Vadose Zone Gas Monitoring				+
Vegetation imaging	Thermal Hyperspectral Imaging (Satellite) Thermal Hyperspectral Imaging (airborne) Colour Infrared (CIR) Transparency Films				+
Atmospheric CO ₂ Flux and Concentration Monitoring	CO ₂ Detectors Eddy Covariance Advanced Leak Detection System Laser Systems Tracers (Isotopes) in CO ₂ Samples Flux Accumulation Chamber Bubble stream chemistry Portable Infrared gas analysers Airborne Laser				+
Other	Ecosystems monitoring				+

Table 2-2 should only be regarded as an indicative list of possible monitoring methods and techniques that might be used to cover the regulatory requirements. The main reasons are the fact that the overview does not take any site-related geological information into account, and also the age of the Guidance Document 2; monitoring methods and techniques for CO₂ storage have experienced a rapid development in recent years (see Chapter 4 for more details).

3 EXISTING INTERNATIONAL MONITORING GUIDELINES

3.1 IEAGHG on-line monitoring selection tool

Selection of suitable monitoring methods for Zar-3 pilot CO₂ storage site is pre-defined and limited by the following Zar-3 site parameters:

1. Site location - onshore
2. Depth - about 1700 m
3. Site type - mature oil and gas field in Jurassic carbonates
4. Land-use at site - agriculture
5. Storage capacity – 75 kt CO₂ max. for the pilot project (total storage capacity was estimated at 0.5 Mt)
6. Duration of CO₂ injection - 5 years for the pilot project

To find the best combination ("applicability matrix") of parameters to be monitored with suitable monitoring methods for the above-mentioned condition, we can use some of "based on best practice" guidelines. A specific, useful and user friendly guideline is the on-line monitoring selection tool named "Interactive Design of Monitoring Programmes for the Geological Storage of CO₂" (IEAGHG tool⁵), developed and designed by the British Geological Survey for the Greenhouse Gas programme of the International Energy Agency (IEAGHG) under the CO₂ Capture & Storage Research Theme. Unfortunately, this tool does not contain any special parameters for carbonate reservoirs; specific monitoring conditions for such a reservoir are discussed in Chapter 4.

This monitoring selection tool has been created to identify and prioritise techniques that could form part of a monitoring programme. The tool helps to design a monitoring programme to monitor a CO₂ storage project during all stages from site characterisation (pre-injection) to closure. It aims to identify the most appropriate methods and techniques that should be evaluated for a given stage of project development. This tool should not be considered as being prescriptive but rather as a decision support tool that encourages evaluation of techniques by providing information on their applicability for a defined storage scenario. It is flexible enough to help design monitoring programmes for different storage scenarios and situations.

The selection tool contains 40 monitoring techniques. For each technique, a full description is available including illustrations and indications of suitability. These techniques are collated for different parameters to be monitored (monitoring aims) to find a "matrix of applicability"; the tool enables selection from 9 monitoring aims in all 4 stages of the storage site life cycle (pre-injection, injection, post-injection and closure).

The monitoring aims mentioned above are not the same as the parameters to be monitored that are defined in the Czech Storage Act, the EU CCS Directive and their Annexes (see Chapter 2). Due to this fact, the monitoring aims from IEAGHG tool need to be connected to one of the group of parameters to be monitored according to points 1.2. and 1.3. of the Annex to the Storage Act (corresponding to the EU CCS Directive,

⁵ <https://ieaghg.org/ccs-resources/monitoring-selection-tool>

Annex 1.1. (e) - (l)), and to the monitoring groups described in the Guidance Document 2.

These connections are described in the text below; the parts in italics represent quotations from the IEAGHG tool description.

1. Monitoring aim "Plume" (plume imaging and tracking in the reservoir) - *The ability to explicitly image the plume of free CO₂ and track its movement in the subsurface may be a pre-requisite for many monitoring programmes. In the early stages of CO₂ injection, plume imaging is likely to involve tracking/mapping free CO₂ in the primary storage reservoir using time-lapse seismic surveying.* The aim "Plume" belongs to the parameters defined in point 1.3. b) of the Annex to the Storage Act, and to the group "Plume" according to the Guidance Document 2.
2. Monitoring aim "Calibrate" (calibration of predictive models) - *Predicting how the CO₂ will be stored over the long-term requires the integration of many geological processes in a predictive model. Such models require detailed site-specific geological knowledge of the reservoir, caprock and overburden. By acquiring monitoring data on key processes and their interactions during and after injection, outputs from the predictive models can be tested and calibrated, enabling the models to be suitably modified or rejected.* The aim "Calibrate" belongs to the parameters defined in point 1.3. b) of the Annex to the Storage Act and to the group "Plume" according to the Guidance Document 2.
3. Monitoring aim "Top-seal" (reservoir top-seal integrity) - *Close monitoring of the reservoir top-seal for evidence of failure or leakage will be important, especially during the injection stage of a project. During this period, and for some time afterwards, reservoir pressures are likely to be significantly elevated immediately beneath the caprock. A maximum permissible (threshold) value is likely to have been determined during site characterisation, prior to injection. Evidence of reducing seal integrity or failure could be obtained from a number of monitoring techniques including direct detection or imaging of CO₂, pressure changes in the reservoir or overburden, or changes in aquifer chemistry.* The aim "Top-seal" belongs to the parameters defined in point 1.3. c) of the Annex to the Storage Act, and to the group "Pathways" according to the Guidance Document 2.
4. Monitoring aim "Overburden" (migration in the overburden. i.e. > 25 m depth – see Fig. 3-1) - *The overburden comprises those rock units lying between the storage reservoir and the land surface. The basal overburden unit comprises the reservoir caprock or top-seal (for the purpose of the decision tool, monitoring the topmost 25 m or so of the overburden is considered under surface leakage). Monitoring in the overburden is likely to be required if CO₂ has migrated from the storage reservoir. Many, though not all, of the techniques deployed for monitoring plume migration in the reservoir, would be equally suitable for monitoring migration in the overburden.* The aim "Overburden" belongs to the parameters defined in point 1.3. c) of the Annex to the Storage Act and to the group "Pathways" according to the Guidance Document 2.

Fig. 3-1: Potential CO₂ migration in the overburden of a storage site
Source: IEAGHG tool⁶

5. Monitoring aim "Processes" (subsurface quantification and fine-scale processes) - *The mass of CO₂ that has been injected for storage must be monitored at the wellhead. However, it may be necessary to provide supporting evidence, through geological monitoring, that the mass of CO₂ within the reservoir is equivalent or comparable to that injected and, within the bounds of uncertainty, that no losses have occurred. Currently, accurate quantification of CO₂ in the subsurface poses a serious technical challenge. State-of-the-art analysis can show that quantitative estimates of CO₂ derived from monitoring datasets are consistent with known injected amounts, but unique verification has not yet been achieved. Deployment of multiple monitoring techniques providing complementary datasets, either in terms of measured property, or in terms of measurement scale, can significantly reduce uncertainty. The aim "Processes" belongs to the parameters defined in point 1.3. c) of the Annex to the Storage Act and to the group "Pathways" according to the Guidance Document 2.*
6. Monitoring aim "Seismicity" (induced seismicity and earth movements) - *In some cases CO₂ injection can lead to increased (micro) seismic activity and may, in some circumstances, lead to ground movements, especially for shallower storage reservoirs. As well as covering safety aspects, such as the geomechanical integrity of the store, microseismic monitoring can also enable advancing CO₂ fronts to be mapped in the subsurface. In favourable situations travelttime and attenuation tomography may allow fluid movements to be*

⁶ https://iea.bgs.ac.uk/v2.4_product/explain_aims.html

mapped. The aim "Seismicity" belongs mainly to the parameters defined in point 1.3. c) of the Annex to the Storage Act, and to the group "Pathways" according to the Guidance Document 2.

7. Monitoring aim "Wellbores" (well integrity) - *The ability of wells to retain CO₂ during the injection, post-injection and post-closure phases, is an important issue in many storage situations. Geomechanical and, in the longer term, geochemical processes, can severely degrade well integrity. Mature hydrocarbon fields, especially onshore, are likely to contain significant numbers of wells of varying ages and styles of completion and abandonment. While new completion materials will greatly enhance the stability of new wells, older wells may need closer monitoring.* The aim "Wellbores" belongs to the parameters defined in point 1.3. c) of the Annex to the Storage Act, and to the group "Pathways" according to the Guidance Document 2.
8. Monitoring aim "Detect" (surface leakage detection, i.e. < 25m depth to air) - *As well as defining storage performance, leakage to surface would be considered a significant irregularity. Monitoring technologies to detect surface leakage may well be routinely deployed prior to injection as part of the site baseline characterisation process. Repeat monitoring may be required to establish natural cycles in background variations. This will be especially relevant for onshore situations where diurnal, seasonal and annual variations in biogenic CO₂ may need to be characterised, so that any future leaks can be identified and compared to background variations.* The aim "Detect" belongs to the parameters defined in point 1.3. a) of the Annex to the Storage Act, and to the group "Environmental" according to the Guidance Document 2.
9. Monitoring aim "Quantify" (surface emissions quantification) - *In the event that leakage to the atmosphere or ocean has been positively identified, quantification may be required to account for these emissions in national inventories, to adjust operator allowances and/or to initiate further financial transactions. Additional monitoring activities, remediation plans, regulator notification and licence conditions may also be affected by the quantified amount of CO₂ leakage. The aim "Quantify" belongs to the parameters defined in point 1.3. a) of the Annex to the Storage Act, and to the group "Environmental" according to the Guidance Document 2.*

The results of the IEAGHG on-line tool runs are shown in Fig. 3-3. They represent a matrix (table), showing the dependence between monitoring aims and monitoring techniques (tools). The cells of the matrix show the suitability of a monitoring technique for the selected aim expressed by numbers from 0 up to 4. The number 0 means "not applicable", number 1 means „possibly applicable“, number 2 means „probably applicable“, number 3 means „definitely applicable“ (where the technique would normally be included to meet a particular monitoring aim and its exclusion may reduce the potential for the aim to be achieved, however, site specific conditions may degrade the efficacy of the technique, or even preclude its deployment) and number 4 means „strongly recommended“ (where the technique would normally be regarded as a *key element in meeting a particular monitoring aim* and its exclusion would reduce the potential for the aim to be achieved, however, site specific conditions may degrade the efficacy of the technique, or even preclude its deployment).

For the application of the IEAGHG on-line tool, we have used the Zar-3 input parameters for the pilot project (see Fig. 3-2), as described in the beginning of this chapter. The injection rate 0.015 Mt per year and duration of 5 years have been chosen.

HIDE PANEL		You are not logged-in		LOGIN	Enter scenario name here ...	NEW	HELP	RUN
Reservoir location		Reservoir depth	Reservoir type	Landuse at site	Monitoring phase	Monitoring aims		Tool package
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Onshore <input type="radio"/> Offshore <input type="radio"/> Both		<input type="radio"/> 0.5-1.5 km <input checked="" type="radio"/> 1.5-2.5 km <input type="radio"/> 2.5-4 km <input type="radio"/> >4 km	<input type="radio"/> Aquifer <input checked="" type="radio"/> Oil <input type="radio"/> Gas <input type="radio"/> Coal	<input type="radio"/> Settled <input checked="" type="radio"/> Agricultural <input type="radio"/> Wooded <input type="radio"/> Arid <input type="radio"/> Protected	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Pre-injection <input type="radio"/> Injection <input type="radio"/> Post-injection <input type="radio"/> Closure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plume <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Top-seal <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Overburden <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Processes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Calibrate <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Detect <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Quantify <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Seismicity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Wellbores	<input type="radio"/> Core <input type="radio"/> Extra <input checked="" type="radio"/> All
0.015	Injection rate (Mt/year)	5	Duration (years)	TOOL CATALOGUE	BENCHMARK	SITES	COSTS	EXPORT PRINT

Fig. 3-2: Selected characteristics of Zar-3 CO₂ storage project.

Tool	Rating %	Plume	Top-Seal	Overburden	Processes	Calibrate	Detect	Quantify	Seismicity	Wellbores
Downhole pressure/temperature	50	1.0	4.0	1.0	3.0	4.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	3.0
Tracers	44	1.0	2.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	2.0	0.0	3.0
Geophysical logs	44	1.0	2.0	2.0	4.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0
3D surface seismic	43	2.7	2.0	2.7	2.7	2.7	0.7	0.0	0.0	2.0
Multicomponent surface seismic	37	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.7	2.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.3
Deep fluid chemistry	24	0.7	1.3	1.3	2.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
2D surface seismic	20	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7
Borehole seismic	19	1.3	1.3	0.7	1.3	1.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7
Integrated tools: behind casing	14	0.3	0.7	0.3	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	1.0
Microseismic monitoring	12	0.7	1.0	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	1.3	0.7
Atmospheric gas concentration	10	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.0	0.0	1.3
Sonar bubble stream detection	9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	0.7	0.0	1.3
Surface-atmospheric gas flux	8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	1.0
Soil gas concentrations	8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	0.3	0.0	1.3
Above-zone pulse testing	8	0.0	0.7	1.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
Satellite interferometry / GPS	7	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0
Airborne spectral imaging	6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
Tiltmeters	6	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.7	0.0
Bubble stream chemistry	5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.3	0.0	0.3
Shallow subsurface geochemistry	5	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.3
Borehole gravimetry	4	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3
Airborne EM	4	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.3
Seismic interferometry	4	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

Fig. 3-3: Matrix of monitoring tools vs. monitoring aims - results of the IEAGHG tool for the Zar-3 CO₂ storage project monitoring.

Fig. 3-3 shows results for the pre-injection phase but they were practically the same for all 4 stages of the storage site lifecycle, i.e. for pre-injection, injection, post-injection and closure phases.

Only 2 tools (monitoring methods) were classified by mark 4 (strongly recommended). The Downhole pressure/temperature tool with rating of 50 % seems to be the most important monitoring tool for the Zar-3 storage site. It was classified by 4 for monitoring aims "Top-Seal" and "Calibrate", and by 3 (definitely applicable) for aims "Processes" and "Wellbores". The Geophysical logs tool with rating 44 % was classified by mark 4 for the aims "Processes" and "Wellbores" and by 3 for the aim "Calibrate". These high scores provide a strong indication that these two groups of monitoring tools/methods should be seriously considered in preparation of the monitoring plan.

The tool Traces was classified by mark 3 for the aims "Detect" and "Wellbores". Surface seismic methods (i.e. tools 3D surface seismic and Multicomponent surface seismic) were classified by mark 2.7 (i.e. between probably applicable and definitely applicable) for the aims "Plume", "Overburden", "Processes" and "Calibrate". In these cases, the recommendation is to seriously consider these methods for Zar-3 site monitoring, taking, however, the site-specific knowledge and information strongly into account.

All other tools were classified by mark 2 or less; the reason this might be the low amount of projected CO₂ injection into the Zar-3 storage reservoir. These low scores indicate a high level of uncertainty connected with the usability of the assessed methods and tools. This uncertainty needs to be solved by additional information input, in particular by closer consideration of site-specific conditions, examples from literature (especially from storage sites located in carbonates), site-specific modelling or test survey campaigns.

In general, the IEAGHG tool represents a very useful instrument for basic overview of applicability of various monitoring methods for various monitoring aims at a roughly defined storage site. Its main drawback is that it does not distinguish between various lithologies, especially between clastic reservoirs and carbonates, where mainly the physical and chemical properties of reservoir rocks differ significantly, which also changes the conditions for application of many monitoring methods, in particular those targeting the deep reservoir itself. Therefore, the results of the tool application need to be considered very useful and informative but, in some cases, also to be taken with care.

3.2 US DOE "Best Practices"

Another valuable source of information about monitoring methods is the publication "Best Practices for: Monitoring, Verification, and Accounting (MVA) for Geologic Storage Projects" (hereinafter referred to as DOE Best Practices), presented by the National Energy Technology Laboratory of the US Department of Energy (DOE/NETL-2017/1847, 2017 revised edition)⁷.

This guideline is based on the United States legislation. Existing regulations in the USA relevant to the geological storage of CO₂ are mainly represented by laws and regulations issued by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA); similarly to the European case, the US monitoring strategies are risk-based. The advantage of the US regulations and guidelines is that they are based on long-term and abundant practical experience with CO₂ storage and CO₂-based Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) operations.

In December 2010, significant steps were made towards defining the regulatory framework for carbon capture and storage (CCS) in the United States when EPA released the Underground Injection Control (UIC) Class VI and Greenhouse Gas Reporting (GHGR) rules⁸. The UIC Program⁹ regulates the injection of all fluids into the subsurface, and the UIC Class VI well rule was developed specifically for injection wells used for geological storage of CO₂. These regulations were developed to protect underground sources of drinking water (USDWs) and to ensure that injection operations do not

⁷ <https://netl.doe.gov/node/5827>

⁸ <https://www.epa.gov/ghgreporting>

⁹ <http://www.epa.gov/uic>

endanger the USDWs or human health. Monitoring techniques that address well integrity, groundwater monitoring, subsurface plume tracking, long-term containment of the injected plume, and soil-gas and surface-air monitoring are all applicable to UIC Class VI Rule requirements.

According to the DOE Best Practices, monitoring technologies can be divided into 3 groups:

1. Atmospheric monitoring
2. Near-surface monitoring
3. Subsurface monitoring

The text below has been adopted from the DOE Best Practices document and describes the main benefits and challenges related to application of particular groups of monitoring techniques.

3.2.1 Atmospheric Monitoring Techniques

Optical CO₂ Sensors

Description: Sensors for intermittent or continuous measurement of CO₂ in air.

Benefits: Sensors can be relatively inexpensive and portable.

Challenges: Difficult to distinguish release from natural variations in ambient-CO₂ emissions.

Atmospheric Tracers

Description: Natural and injected chemical compounds that are monitored in air to help detect CO₂ released to the atmosphere.

Benefits: Used as a proxy for CO₂, when direct observation of a CO₂ release is not adequate. Also used to track potential CO₂ plumes.

Challenges: In some cases, analytical equipment is not available onsite, and samples need to be analysed offsite. Background/baseline levels must be established. Tracers may not behave the same as CO₂ along the migration pathway.

Eddy Covariance

Description: Flux measurement technique used to measure atmospheric CO₂ concentrations at a specified height above the ground surface.

Benefits: Can provide continuous data, averaged over both time and space, over a large area (hundreds of meters to several kilometres).

Challenges: Specialized equipment and robust data processing are required. Natural spatial and temporal variability in CO₂ flux may mask release signal.

3.2.2 Near-Surface Monitoring

Geochemical Monitoring in the Soil and Vadose Zone

Description: Sampling of soil gas for CO₂, natural chemical tracers, and introduced tracers. Measurements are made by extracting gas samples from shallow wells or from/with flux accumulation chambers placed on the soil surface and/or with sensors inserted into the soil.

Benefits: Soil-gas measurements detect shifts in gas ratios or elevated CO₂ concentrations above background levels that may provide indications of gas releases from depth. Tracers aid in identification of native vs. injected CO₂. Flux chambers can quickly and accurately measure local CO₂ fluxes from soil to air.

Challenges: Potential for interference from surface processes producing false positives as well as missing signal is significant. Significant effort for potential lack of significant results. Relatively late detection of release. Considerable effort is required to avoid cross-contamination of tracer samples. Natural analogues suggest that migration may be focused in small areas and flux chambers provide measurements for a limited area.

Geochemical Monitoring of Shallow Groundwater

Description: Geochemical sampling of shallow groundwater above CO₂ storage reservoir to demonstrate isolation of the reservoir from USDWs. Chemical analyses may include pH, alkalinity, electrical conductivity, major and minor elements, dissolved gasses, tracers, and many other parameters. Sensor probes/meters, as well as titration test kits, can be used to test/ sample in the field.

Benefits: Mature technology, samples collected with shallow monitoring wells. Sensors may be inserted into the aquifer. Address major regulatory concern regarding migration reaching USDWs, and may have value in responding to local concerns, which typically elevate concerns about groundwater.

Challenges: Significant effort for potential lack of significant results. Reactive transport modelling of CO₂ migration shows that signal may be retarded and attenuated so that high well density and long sampling periods are required to reach an insignificant result. Many factors other than fluids from depth can change or damage aquifer water quality, and detailed assessment of aquifer flow system may be needed to attribute a change to signal either to migration or to other factors. Gas solubility and associated parameters (pH, alkalinity) are pressure sensitive, so that obtaining samples representative of the aquifer fluids requires careful sampling. Carbon isotopes may be difficult to interpret due to complex interactions with carbonate minerals in shallow formations.

Surface Displacement Monitoring (Includes Remote Sensing)

Description: Monitor surface deformation caused by reservoir pressure changes or geomechanical impacts associated with CO₂ injection. Measurements made with satellite-based radar (SAR/InSAR) and surface- and subsurface-based tiltmeters and GPS instruments. Data allow modelling of injection-induced fracturing and volumetric change in the reservoir.

Benefits: Highly precise measurements over a large area (100 km x 100 km) can be used to track pressure changes or geomechanical impacts in the subsurface associated with plume migration. Tiltmeter technology is mature, and has been used successfully for monitoring steam/water injection and hydraulic fracturing in oil and gas fields. GPS measurements complement InSAR and tiltmeter data.

Challenges: Tiltmeters and GPS measurements require surface/subsurface access and remote data collection. InSAR methods work well in locations with level terrain, minimal vegetation, and minimal land use, but must be modified for complex terrain/ varied conditions. Surface displacement responds also to groundwater withdrawal and recharge and to non-injection related process such as local to regional subsidence and uplift. Movement may not indicate risk, must be coupled with complex 3D geomechanical models to make results actionable.

Ecosystem Stress Monitoring (Includes Remote Sensing)

Description: Satellite imagery, aerial photography, and spectral imagery are used to measure vegetative stress resulting from elevated CO₂ in soil or air. Ground-based study is required to develop understanding of signal to train the image processing and validate anomalies detected.

Benefits: Imaging techniques can cover large areas, at relatively high frequency and low cost, and image processing can be automated. Vegetative stress is proportional to soil CO₂ levels and proximity to CO₂ release.

Challenges: Detection only possible after sustained CO₂ emissions have occurred. Shorter duration release may not be detectable. Natural variations in site conditions make it difficult to establish reliable baseline. Changes not related to CO₂ release can lead to false positives. Variable sensitivity of vegetation to CO₂ and small areas of focus release can lead to missed signal.

3.2.3 Surface Monitoring

Wireline Deployed Well Logging Tools

Description: Mature technology in which tools lowered into wells on wireline cables (so that the tool is in communication with the surface) are slowly moved up the well collecting data designed to monitor the condition of the wellbore and changes in fluids in the near-wellbore environment. Examples of logs used in geologic storage monitoring include acoustic (sonics), resistivity, borehole diameter logging, and pulsed neutron capture.

Benefits: Commercial technology used to assess the condition of the well casing and cement and changes in near-wellbore fluid or formation composition. Under favourable conditions, log response may be highly sensitive to CO₂ outside the wellbore. No need to perforate well to detect CO₂.

Challenges: Area of investigation limited to near the wellbore. Sensitivity of tool to fluid change varies; only under optimum conditions are tools sensitive to dissolved CO₂ or changes in mineralogy. Working fluids in wells may affect log results. Logging requires wells that penetrate the interval of interest and mobilization costs may be substantive, limiting repeated surveys. If a well is perforated in an area charged with CO₂ access, the well requires pressure management. Both wireline and well casing may

corrode, especially in the presence of CO₂, requiring management via metallurgy or corrosion inhibition.

Wellbore Deployed Pressure and Temperature

Description: A large array of gauges is available to measure pressure and temperature. Technology is mature. Gauges are deployed at wellhead and can be permanently installed on casing, semi permanently deployed on tubing, or intermittently emplaced on slickline. Wireline communications are standard with the casing and tubing deployments; the intermittent emplacement may either be on wireline or use internal memory and be retrieved. Gauges may be deployed both on injection wells and on monitoring wells distant from injection intervals.

Benefits: Reservoir pressure is a key parameter in the EPA UIC Class VI Program, and because of the complex temperature and pressure effects on fluid density, direct measurements at the reservoir may be needed to augment and calibrate standard wellhead pressure measurements. Measurements of reservoir response to changes in injection pressure is a mature tool for assessing fluid flow and hydrologic properties and is a key input for history-matching simulation models.

Challenges: Gauges must be in communication with the reservoir. If the gauge is run inside of the casing, then the well must be perforated and thus the entire well is potentially exposed to corrosive fluids, increased pressure, and potential changes in wellbore fluids that may alter monitoring technologies run from inside of it (e.g., seismic). Gauges run outside of casing are not retrievable, must be carefully placed to exclude cement between the gauge and the reservoir, and must have an umbilical back to the wellhead that is a potential leakage path.

Wellbore- Based Fluid Monitoring Tools

Description: Geochemical sampling is required under EPA's UIC Class VI to quantify the composition of the injected fluid. Fluid sampling can also be conducted at wells distant from injection wells to assess breakthrough of CO₂ or rock-CO₂ water reactions using surface or downhole samplers.

Benefits: Modelling the response of the reservoir to injection.

Challenges: Assessing chemistry of CO₂-brine pore fluids in the rock matrix presents many challenges related to pressure and temperature dependence of solubility and the complexity of accurately sampling mixed density-mixed viscosity brine and CO₂ in the well construction.

Emerging Wellbore Tools

Description: Emerging wellbore technologies include smart sensors for geologic storage monitoring applications and subsurface tracer applications. Tools include harmonic pulse testing of reservoirs, modular borehole monitoring, and novel tracers.

Benefits: Demonstrate reservoir integrity through pressure response during pulse testing. The modular borehole monitoring (MBM) concept is a multi-functional suite of instruments designed to optimize subsurface monitoring. Geochemical changes associated with the interaction of injected tracers and supercritical CO₂ provide insight concerning migration of CO₂ through the reservoir.

Challenges: Reservoir noise interference and signal-to-noise ratio may be an issue.

Seismic Geophysical Methods

Description: Seismic geophysical methods use acoustic energy to image the subsurface. Differences between the acoustic properties of CO₂ and other fluids enable the plume monitoring by seismic methods. Active seismic methods (surface seismic reflection, VSP, cross-well) require a source and receiver. Passive seismic methods use natural subsurface processes that emit acoustic energy from fracture development or slip on a fault.

Benefits: Substitution of CO₂ for brine under many conditions creates a strong change in seismic velocity ideal for time-lapse quantification from pre-injection baseline (brine-filled) pores to pores partly filled with CO₂. Reflection seismic under the right conditions is useful both for time-lapse monitoring of a CO₂ plume and for identification of any out-of-zone CO₂ accumulation indicating a release. Surface seismic surveys can assess large areas and large thicknesses completely (as compared to point measurements). Borehole seismic (crosswell, VSP) surveys can provide higher-resolution imaging near or between wellbores. Passive seismic (microseismic monitoring) can be used to detect natural and induced seismicity, to map faults and fractures in the injection zone and adjacent horizons, and to track the migration of the fluid pressure front.

Challenges: Repeatability of seismic survey needed for time-lapse surveys may be difficult under varying surface conditions. Geologic complexity and a noisy recording environment can degrade or attenuate surface seismic data and the presence of gas in baseline fluids can reduce detection of CO₂. Borehole seismic methods require a wellbore for monitoring, and for crosswell, the distance between wells containing the source and receivers may limit success of the survey due to source strength constraints. A comprehensive knowledge of reservoir geomechanical properties is needed to properly interpret microseismic events for migration of the pressure front.

Gravity Methods

Description: Use of gravity measurements to monitor changes in density of fluid resulting from injection of CO₂, which is substituted for brine or other reservoir fluids.

Benefits: Gravity measurement provides a direct assessment of the parameter wanted, mass of CO₂, unlike all other measures, which are proxies and must be converted by modelling into an estimate of mass.

Challenges: Technology is still maturing. Limited detection and resolution unless gravimeters are located just above reservoir, which significantly increases cost. Noise and gravity variations (tides, drift) need to be eliminated to interpret gravity anomalies due to CO₂.

Electrical Methods

Description: Based on the resistivity contrast between injected CO₂ and more conductive brine, can be used in time-lapse. Technology used in the oil and gas industry to detect hydrocarbons. Electrical methods used in geologic storage projects are (1) electrical resistance tomography (ERT) and electromagnetic (EM) tomography that images spatial distribution of resistivity in reservoir by measuring potential differences and (2) controlled-source electromagnetic (CSEM) surveys that measure induced electrical and magnetic fields.

Benefits: Electrical techniques provide resistivity distribution in the subsurface, which can be interpreted to estimate CO₂ saturation distribution. Data resolution is dependent on electrode spacing for ERT techniques. Crosswell ERT is more sensitive to changes in near-wellbore resistivity. Surface-downhole ERT and CSEM measurements increase the lateral extent and provide data on CO₂ plume tracking. ERT and CSEM do not interfere with other subsurface monitoring techniques operating within the well casing (e.g., wireline logging, borehole seismic).

Challenges: May not detect contrast between CO₂ and hydrocarbons. ERT, EM tomography, and CSEM surveys require non-conductive well casings and multiple monitoring wells. Deployment and inversion are less mature than other technologies.

The DOE Best Practices are based on a different system of regulations and requirements than the European Guidance Document 2 or the IEAGHG tool. The US CO₂ geological storage regulation is oriented to injection wells definition, namely the Underground Injection Control (UIC) Class VI well rule was developed specifically for injection wells used for geologic storage of CO₂ and to protect underground sources of drinking water. Nevertheless, groundwater protection is a very important issue of CO₂ storage in general, particularly for onshore storage. The recommendations of the DOE Best Practices are hence very relevant for the Zar-3 site as well, and were carefully considered. Most of the methods and tools coincide with the European approach but some useful additions to the results obtained from the IEAGHG tool could be identified.

In particular, the item "Geochemical Monitoring of Shallow Groundwater", i.e. geochemical sampling of shallow groundwater above CO₂ storage reservoir to demonstrate isolation of the reservoir from groundwater source, has been found very relevant and was added to the list and matrix of suitable monitoring methods. In addition, the item "Emerging Wellbore Tools" (smart sensors for geologic storage monitoring applications and subsurface tracer applications, e.g. harmonic pulse testing of reservoirs, modular borehole monitoring, and novel tracers) is recommended for further consideration and discussion.

4 EXPERIENCE WITH MONITORING OF CO₂ STORAGE IN CARBONATES

4.1 Literature review focused on the monitoring of CO₂ storage projects in carbonate reservoir rocks

Another valuable source of information for the selection of appropriate monitoring methods for the Zar-3 site is the published experience with monitoring of CO₂ storage in other carbonate reservoirs worldwide. This is based on the supposed analogy of the geological and lithological properties of Zar-3 with the known cases of carbonate reservoirs where CO₂ injection and monitoring took place.

Despite the CCS has undergone a significant development in recent decades, there are only a few examples of projects, where the carbonate reservoirs have been used (or projected to be used) for CO₂ storage or its combination with CO₂-EOR. A summary of the most important CO₂ storage projects focused on carbonate rocks, including the planned/used monitoring methods, is provided in Tab. 4-1. In general, major monitoring and research objectives of these projects include CO₂ plume tracking, CO₂-reservoir rock reactivity, storage potential, trapping efficiency, cap rock integrity, risk of leakage, models verification & calibration, recording of induced seismicity, well design & integrity and public acceptance.

Tab. 4-1 Examples of important CO₂ storage projects focused on carbonate reservoirs including planned/used monitoring methods.

Project / Site	Selected monitoring methods	Reference
Niagaran pinnacle reefs (Michigan, USA)	Vertical seismic profiling; Distributed temperature sensing; Distributed acoustic sensing; Borehole gravity; Pulsed neutron logging; Cross-well seismic; Borehole temperature + pressure monitoring; Reservoir fluids geochemical analysis; Tracer injection; Microseismic monitoring; Wellhead injection rate measurements; Interferometric synthetic aperture radar (InSAR)	Gupta et al. (2013) Gupta et al. (2017) Conner et al. (2017) Kelley et al. (2020)
Hontomín (Spain)	Surface 4D seismic; 4D Vertical seismic profiling; 3D (micro-)gravity; 4D Controlled source electromagnetic; 4D Electrical resistivity tomography; Microseismic time reversal imaging; High resolution noise interferometry; Borehole temperature + pressure monitoring; Water geochemical analysis; CO ₂ detectors; Isotopic analysis; Soil gas flux; Hydrogeological monitoring; Bioindicators; Differential interferometric synthetic aperture radar + Ground-based SAR	Pérez-Estaún (2012) ¹⁰ Andrés et al. (2016) Elío et al. (2013) Vilamajó et al. (2013)

¹⁰ http://www.cgseurope.net/UserFiles/file/madrid,%20sept%202012/presentations/Hontomin_Perez-Estaun.pdf

Weyburn-Midale (Saskatchewan, Canada)	4D seismic, 4D vertical seismic profiling; Tracer injection; Production data analysis (EOR); Borehole temperature + pressure monitoring; Geophysical logging; Water geochemical analysis; Soil gas flux and soil CO ₂ concentrations; Mobile infrared laser; Airborne electromagnetics	Bellefleur et al. (2003) Preston et al. (2009) White (2009, 2011) Jenkins et al. (2015)
Fort Nelson (British Columbia, Canada)	Multicomponent surface seismic; Microseismic (well-based); Vertical seismic profiling; Wellhead injection rate measurements; Downhole fluid chemistry/geochemistry; pH measurements; Tracer injection; Geophysical and well integrity logs; Surface and downhole pressure + temperature monitoring	Gorecki et al. (2012) Sorensen et al. (2013)

Two of the sites shown in Tab. 4-1 have not reached the full injection phase: CO₂ injection at the Hontomín storage pilot site has been put on hold prematurely in 2019, before the main injection phase planned within the ENOS project¹¹. Due to this, most of the planned monitoring work has not been realised. The overall amount of CO₂ stored on the site up to now is only 3 kt. The Fort Nelson project has been put on hold in 2016, before realisation. In both cases, the overview of monitoring methods reflects just the monitoring plans and, in case of Hontomín, surveys corresponding to the baseline phase. Repeat measurements have not been performed in most cases.

The two sites that provide the most valuable practical monitoring experience are Weyburn-Midale and the Niagaran pinnacle reefs. In both cases CO₂ storage is combined with CO₂-driven Enhanced Oil Recovery (CO₂-EOR) but monitoring of CO₂ injection and its behaviour has been an important component of the projects and the published monitoring results represent an invaluable input in monitoring plans at similar geological settings.

Monitoring of CO₂-EOR and associated CO₂ storage at the Weyburn-Midale field in Southeastern Saskatchewan, Canada, has been performed in conjunction with large-scale commercial enhanced oil recovery activities carried out at the fields by the EnCana and later Apache companies since 2000, following baseline data collection surveys (Preston et al. 2009). The work was led by the Petroleum Research Centre in Regina, putting together a broad number of research organisations and technological companies from around the world.

The Weyburn-Midale field is located in the northern part of the Williston basin. Its Weyburn pool is a large oil field of ca. 180 km² in area, originally containing about 225 million m³ of oil in place (Whittaker 2004). The Midale pool is slightly smaller and it is situated immediately to the east of the Weyburn pool (Jensen et al. 2009). The structure of the Weyburn-Midale field is formed by gently SW dipping (8 to 10 m/km) strata of Mississippian-aged carbonates, progressively truncated to the north by sub-Mesozoic unconformity. The seal is provided by an up to 10 m thick anhydrite layer, the Midale evaporite above the reservoir and by the Triassic red beds and evaporite beds of the Watrous formation above the unconformity (e.g. Jensen et al. 2009, Njiekak et al., 2013).

¹¹ <http://www.enos-project.eu/>

The reservoir of the Weyburn-Midale field is situated in the Mississippian (Lower Carboniferous) Midale beds of the Charles formation at a depth interval of approximately 1400 to 1430 m below the surface. The Midale beds are interpreted as having formed in an arid tidal-flat environment on a low-relief carbonate shelf (Pendrih 2005). The lower layer of the reservoir, formed by more permeable and fractured limestone unit termed “Vuggy” is around 15 m thick and contains porous shoal deposits (porosity up to 20 %, average permeability 50 mD) and the intershoal sediments (porosity up to 12 %, average permeability 3 mD). The upper, low-permeability (porosities up to 38 %, average permeability 10 mD) unit locally known as “Marly” is a chalky dolostone with an average thickness of about 6 m (e.g. Whittaker 2004, Njiekak et al., 2013).

In general, the Weyburn-Midale field is geologically rather different from the Zar-3 structure and the main similarity lies in the lithology. Nevertheless, since this is one of only a few practical cases of CO₂ storage in carbonates, the experience with the use of monitoring methods is worth considering, especially with those focusing on the reservoir itself.

Good monitoring results were achieved at both Weyburn and Midale pools by using the 4D (i.e. time-lapse 3D) seismic that was able - also thanks to advanced data processing - to monitor the CO₂ flood in the reservoir, track the extent of the corresponding CO₂ plume and map possible changes in the caprock and overburden (White, 2011). The seismic surveys were successfully complemented by downhole pressure measurements and downhole fluid sampling. Shallow monitoring data, especially from atmogeochemical, shallow geochemical and groundwater monitoring, were helpful, i.e., in refuting widely publicised claims of surface leakage. Passive seismic monitoring has been beneficial for public assurance, notably with respect to demonstrating a lack of induced earthquakes. Oppositely, the electrical resistance tomography and microgravimetry were considered insufficiently sensitive for use at Weyburn-Midale, while InSAR was thought to have potential application (Jenkins et al. 2015).

The Niagaran pinnacle reefs (full name Northern Niagaran Pinnacle Reef Trend, NNPRT) in northern Michigan, USA, have been investigated by the Midwest Regional Carbon Sequestration Partnership (MRCSP¹²) under the leadership of the Battelle Memorial Institute, Columbus, Ohio. Selected reefs at various stages of CO₂-EOR development were used as test beds for understanding geoscience issues and developing best practices related to all aspects of CO₂-EOR and subsequent CO₂ storage, including monitoring (Gupta et al., 2013 and 2017).

The NNPRT oil and gas fields are situated within the Silurian Guelph formation of the Niagaran group, characterized regionally by the development of barrier reef complexes and individual “pinnacle” reefs in more basinward positions. Individual reefs are closely-spaced, but highly geologically compartmentalized and laterally discontinuous. The fields are generally of small areal extent (0.2 – 1.6 km², average 0.32 km², largest about 8.0 km²), high relief (up to 215 m), and steep flanks (30° to 45°), they are effectively sealed by the lower Salina evaporite (halite and anhydrite) deposits. Average production from the largest oil fields in the NNPRT is more than 80 000 m³ of cumulative oil per field (Barnes et al. 2013).

The reservoir facies primarily consist of porous and permeable dolomite with both intercrystalline and touching vug pore types. Some reefs are completely dolomitized, while others are essentially all limestone. Effective porosity intervals for the reservoir

¹² <https://www.mrcsp.org/>

range from only a few meters in some reefs to several hundred meters in other reefs. The best reservoir rocks are associated with dolomitized reef core and foreslope reef lithofacies and well-developed intercrystalline and vuggy porosity. Porosity values may reach 35 % but typically average between 3 and 12 %, permeability is between 3 and 10 mD but can be significantly higher if fractures intersect matrix porosity (Barnes et al. 2013, Haagsma et al. 2017).

In summary, it appears that NNPRT fields are somewhat similar to the Zar-3 site, especially regarding the reservoir. This similarity includes mainly reservoir lithology and porosity, structure relief, areal and vertical extent of the fields and trap type, i.e. practically most of the basic geological features and possibly also depositional settings. Thanks to this, it can be expected that monitoring methods that proved to generate successful results in monitoring of CO₂ storage in the NNPRT reefs might also be appropriate for monitoring purposes at Zar-3.

The monitoring programme performed at the Niagaran pinnacle reefs by the MRCSP partnership has been quite comprehensive. Earlier phases of testing of various monitoring methods confirmed the usefulness of downhole pressure and temperature monitoring, microseismic monitoring, and partly InSAR (Gupta et al., 2017).

A very good summary of results achieved by MRCSP in the most recent phase of testing has been provided by Kelley et al. (2020)¹³. According to this source, the most useful monitoring methods (with the highest efficacy rating) were distributed temperature sensing (DTS; rating 2.5 out of 3), borehole gravity (rating 2.0) and geochemical monitoring (rating 2.0). Cross-well seismic (rating 0.5) and pulsed neutron logging (rating 0.5) brought encouraging but unequivocal results, while, surprisingly, the vertical seismic profiling (VSP) in both classical setting and combined with use of distributed acoustic sensing (DAS-VSP) were evaluated as inconclusive. It should also be noticed that the carbonate pinnacle reefs were found to be a difficult environment for seismic technologies – all three seismic technologies that were used (cross-well, VSP, DAS-VSP) had limited success in delineating the distribution of CO₂ in the reservoir. This might be a warning signal for possible plans to use seismic methods for monitoring the CO₂ storage at Zar-3.

The monitoring efforts at the Niagaran pinnacle reefs included a small number of novel monitoring methods that have been successfully tested in practice. Those are mainly pulsed neutron (capture) logging (PNL or PNC logging), distributed temperature sensing (DTS) and borehole gravity surveys.

Gupta et al. (2013) and Conner et al. (2017) discuss the feasibility of pulsed neutron (capture) logging (PNL) for monitoring and modelling of CO₂ behaviour in the carbonate reefs. The purpose of PNL is to characterize the vertical distribution of fluids adjacent to wellbore to help monitoring the migration of injected CO₂ through the reservoir during CO₂-EOR and/or CO₂ injection. All accessible wells situated within each reef were subject to periodical monitoring by PNL during CO₂-injection (Gupta et al., 2013). The logging method is applicable in both open- and cased-hole environments. In general, PNC logs operate by generating a pulse of high energy neutrons, subsequently measuring the neutron decay over time and across a wide energy spectrum. The method measures the ability of an element to capture thermal neutrons and generates a log of this value (so called sigma value), which is compared to referenced values of common downhole fluids and formation matrices. A higher sigma value equates to a greater ability of a particular

¹³ including the presentation by M. Kelley at the GHGT-15 conference in March 2021 that included additional, yet unpublished results

element to capture, or absorb, the neutrons (Conner et al., 2017). Formation brines, oil, natural gases and CO₂ all have distinctive sigma values which can be used for determining fluid saturations at various depths surrounding the borehole (Conner et al., 2017). PNC logging may be a useful monitoring tool for the Zar-3 field as it can provide reliable information on the distribution of reservoir fluids along the wellbore and distinguish relatively small amounts of injected CO₂.

Mawalkar et al. (2019) and Kelley et al. (2020) demonstrate the feasibility of distributed temperature sensing (DTS) for CO₂ storage monitoring in the carbonate reefs. The DTS was primarily used to determine the distribution of CO₂ inflow zones, but it also complemented the understanding of flow stratification in the reservoir and possible vertical fluids migration along the borehole. The DTS uses fibre-optic cables as temperature sensors. Generally, fibre-optic cables can be permanently installed in boreholes, either cemented behind the casing or deployed on the production tube (Correa et al., 2019). In principle, the fibre-optic cable is interrogated using a laser pulse, the assemblage of returned light signals over time is analysed. The returned light signal is the result of backscattered light waves released by atoms in the matrix of the fibre in reaction to the initial laser pulse (Mawalkar et al., 2019). The timing of a given returned signal is related to the location of that measurement on the fibre and the character and magnitude of the returned signal is used to compute the temperature at that point (Mawalkar et al., 2019). According to Kelley et al. (2020), the DTS has one of the highest efficacy ratings among the monitoring methods used at the Niagaran reefs, and as such should be considered as an option for the monitoring plan at Zar-3.

Gupta et al. (2017) discuss the feasibility of borehole gravity logging for identification, correlation and imaging of subsurface structures and stratigraphy of the Niagaran reefs. However, the method was also successfully used for determination of temporal gravity anomalies related to CO₂ injection. Gravity and depth differences measured between successive stations were used to create the interval vertical gradient of gravity, which varied inversely with the density of the rock layer bracketed by the measurements. Borehole gravity data were converted to the apparent or interval density profiles suitable for evaluation of changes in the reservoir related to the injection of CO₂. This method has been evaluated as one of the efficient monitoring methods used at the Niagaran reefs (Kelley et al., 2020) and is therefore recommended for consideration at the Zar-3 site as well.

4.2 Other novel CO₂ storage monitoring methods

In addition to the above-mentioned results of CO₂ storage monitoring in carbonate reservoir rocks, several other novel monitoring methods have made their mark in other, non-carbonate focused, CO₂ storage projects.

Correa et al. (2019) demonstrate the performance of distributed acoustic sensing (DAS) combined with 3D surface seismic survey applications and vertical seismic profiling (VSP) for subsurface and CO₂ plume monitoring in the Otway project (Australia). DAS data are acquired by connecting a fibre-optic cable to an interrogator unit, which sends a series of laser pulses along the fibre. DAS senses change of strain on the cable by analysing variations in the backscattered light. Correa et al. (2019) used standard fibre-optic cables permanently installed on the production tubing of the injector well to acquire on-demand VSP data at fine spatial sampling. The method offers certain

advantages over geophones, such as long equipment survivability, dense spatial sampling, and full well coverage, making it especially suited for permanent reservoir monitoring. Recently, the DAS-VSP was also deployed at the Niagaran carbonate reefs by MRCSP, however, with no significant success (Kelley et al., 2020) – see above.

Jenkins et al. (2015) and Bui et al. (2018) present a successful demonstration of the use of Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR) technology to monitor movements in surface elevation over the injection site. At the In Salah site (Algeria), the inexpensive InSAR combined with pressure monitoring data was effective in diagnosing both the leakage of CO₂ into the cap rock and fractures in the cap rock induced by overpressuring of the system during injection. However, the groundwater use in the area can limit the sensitivity of the method compared to the ideal situation at In Salah. The method may be possibly recommended also for the Zar-3 site, but installation of permanent scatterers (PSInSAR) will be required due to the seasonal changes in the vegetation cover, similarly to several other projects (Pearce et al., 2005). Moreover, the sensitivity of the method cannot be guaranteed due to the relatively small presumed amount of injected CO₂. Other methods, such as Tiltmeters and Differential Global Positioning System (DGPS) may substitute or complement the InSAR technology.

Burba et al. (2013) present the advantages of the eddy covariance method for CO₂ storage projects. The eddy covariance (or eddy flux) is a surface-based, micrometeorological monitoring method useful for detecting and quantifying potential CO₂ leakage from the storage site. It may be used for effective and relatively cheap continuous monitoring of the storage site, including the post-closure phase. Using this method, the CO₂ flux can be computed directly from the in-situ measurements of the surface-to-atmosphere gas emissions in the turbulent air flow above the surface. Such conditions can be imagined as a horizontal flow of numerous rotating “eddies” each characterized by its 3D components, including vertical movement of the air (Burba et al., 2013). This monitoring method can cover an area of up to tens of square kilometres, which would be sufficient for the Zar-3 site.

Research and development efforts have been recently made to improve the above-surface monitoring methods that would be able to identify CO₂ leakage, covering, at the same time large monitoring areas. US DOE evaluated advanced leak detection systems composed of a sensitive multi-gas detector (CH₄, total HC, CO₂) with a GPS mapping system carried by aircraft, drone or terrestrial vehicles (Plasynski et al., 2011). Satellite or airplane-based optical methods used for the ecosystem stress monitoring and changes in vegetation integrity may be also used for CO₂ leakage identification at CO₂ storage projects.

5 AVAILABLE DATASETS AT ZAR-3

The Zar-3 site is a mature crude oil and natural gas field, opened for production in 2002. Since the opening year, MND, the operator of Zar-3 field, has carried out various measurements commonly associated with hydrocarbon production, e.g. measurements of wellhead and reservoir temperature and pressure. The quantity of produced oil and gas, as well as reservoir (or surrounding aquifer) water has been registered. There are 14 wells at the Zar-3 field; and well-log data (at least SP and resistivity methods) have been recorded in all of them. These data can be used for baseline characteristics of reservoir conditions before CO₂ injection. 3D seismic, recorded here in 1994 and 2004, represents another available dataset for baseline characteristics.

The following datasets are recommended for evaluation and further use for the purposes of CO₂ storage site monitoring at Zar-3:

- 3D seismic dataset.** 3D seismic covers the whole area of the Zar-3 reservoir structure and surrounding area of interest. The 3D seismic acquisition from 1994 used dynamite technology with nominal fold 15, the newer 3D seismic from 2004 used vibroseis technology with nominal fold 30-40. Seismic data available for project purposes cover an area of about 15 km² and represent the result of merging of both acquisition stages and new data reprocessing. The 3D seismic cube consists of in-lines of SW - NE direction and cross-lines of SE - NW direction with 25 m interval between individual seismic lines. Fig. 5-1 shows a sample seismic cross-section derived from the 3D data cube with highlighted reservoir shapes and well paths. The 3D seismic can be used as a baseline for subsequent regular monitoring of CO₂ storage in the reservoir, in particular for tracking the CO₂ plume during and after injection (4D seismic), in case the planned applicability study confirms sufficient resolution of the method for this purpose.

Fig. 5-1: Zar-3 field seismic inline 2423.

- Well logging.** Standard well logging methods – GR (gamma ray), SP (spontaneous potential), DDN (Dual Detector Neutron logging), resistivity methods, sonic and density logs are available for most of the wells. Due to reservoir rock lithology (naturally fractured carbonate reservoir), also specific logs focused mainly on fractures and their properties are available - these include FMS (Formation Micro Scanner) in wells ZA3, ZA4a, ZA5H, ZA6aH, ZA7 and FMI (Formation Micro Imager) in the well ZA14H. These logs provide important information about fractures, like e.g. density, orientation (azimuth, dip) and possible conductivity (Fig. 5-2). Open-hole intervals still exist in all horizontal wells and most of the slanted wells. The length of the open-hole intervals can now be smaller than before the start of production because of the increased length of casing providing the water / gas isolation during production. The existence of open-hole intervals should allow execution of repeated logging, which can, i. a., provide valuable information on CO₂ interactions with reservoir rocks (carbonates), their effect on the properties of fractures and the whole reservoir, as well as other changes induced by CO₂ injection.

Fig. 5-2: FMS logging output from the ZA5aH well.

- Borehole seismic datasets.** Vertical seismic profiling (VSP) and check-shots were performed in wells ZA3 and ZA7. Borehole seismic measurements were used for correlation with surface seismic data and for obtaining images of higher resolution than those based on surface seismic data. The availability of borehole seismic data provides an opportunity for repeat measurements that can be (under favourable conditions) used for monitoring of changes in the reservoir and possibly its overburden.
- Pressure, temperature, reservoir fluid properties, PVT.** There are regular initial data available for each well (after drilling), such as reservoir pressure,

temperature and original reservoir fluids properties. There is also a PVT analysis from the ZA3 well that provides important reservoir fluid information (R_s – solution gas-oil ratio, viscosity, P_{sat} – saturation pressure) before the start of production, i.e. information about initial reservoir conditions. Reservoir pressure and temperature changes in relation to production over time are available from the observation well ZA3. This regular monitoring activity (primarily for hydrocarbon production) will continue during CO_2 injection and later during the post-injection storage phase, comprising fluid analyses, pressure and temperature measurements). For future CO_2 injection activities, all surface facilities and well-heads will be equipped with the necessary supplementary components needed for monitoring of the injected CO_2 . Pressure and temperature measurements, both at wellhead and at reservoir level, are mandatory monitoring technologies (Annex to the Storage Act, point 1.2.).

- Monitoring of gas-oil and water-oil contacts (GOC, WOC).** Changes of oil zone thickness and position of GOC and WOC during production have been monitored in the observation well ZA3 (Fig. 5-3). These data represent a valuable baseline for subsequent monitoring of the behaviour of the mixture of injected CO_2 and the remaining reservoir fluids.

Fig. 5-3: GOC and WOC monitoring in the ZA3 well.

The complete dataset available to CO_2 -SPICER from MND monitoring and observation of the Zar-3 field during the exploration and production periods represents a huge amount of valuable original field data and evidence of their development over time. A large part of the data can be used as baseline for monitoring of CO_2 storage in the next phase of field development.

6 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR SELECTION OF MONITORING METHODS FOR ZAR-3

Using information gathered from the Guidance Document 2 (Chapter 2), the IEAGHG tool, the DOE Best Practices (Chapter 3) and the literature overview (Chapter 4), recommendations can be drawn for selection of monitoring technologies (techniques, methods) that will meet the conditions defined by legislation, in particular points 1.2. and 1.3. of the Annex to the Storage Act and cover all 4 stages of the storage site life cycle.

Ten monitoring techniques have been selected for this recommendation; they are described below. Text in italic indicates quotations from the IEAGHG tool or from the DOE Best Practices.

1) Downhole pressure / temperature measurements

- Technology characterization according to the IEAGHG tool: *Downhole instrumentation for measuring pressure and temperature is strongly recommended as part of any CO₂ injection operation. These parameters can be diagnostic of reservoir mechanical integrity, possible leakage from the reservoir or from a well and also of the physical properties of the injected CO₂. Baseline data will be useful, particularly when the site is an operational or depleted hydrocarbon reservoir.*
- The IEAGHG tool rating of this technology is high (50 %) and it is strongly recommended for "Top-seal" and "Calibrate" aims of monitoring. The method is also recommended by the DOE Best Practices as "Wellbore Deployed Pressure and Temperature" and by Guidance Document 2 as "Pressure and Temperature" for parameters group "Plume" monitoring. This technology fulfils the conditions defined by point 1.2. (mandatory monitored parameters) and point 1.3, letters b) and c) of the Annex to the Storage Act.
- Baseline data are available at MND for the period of field production history.

2) Geophysical logs

- Technology characterization according to the IEAGHG tool: *One of the most common methods of evaluating downhole properties and conditions is by wireline logging, a mature technology that has been highly developed by the petroleum industry. Wireline logs are acquired by lowering geophysical instruments (tools) down the well and making a measurement profile of various physical properties along its length as the tools are pulled back out. The presence of CO₂ can change the physical properties of the borehole such that under favourable conditions these changes may be detected and measured by the well logging tools. Pre-injection surveys are important to assess baseline conditions and may also be useful for determining the most appropriate tools for CO₂ monitoring. A time lapse series of wireline logs, run both during and post-injection, can be used to monitor the behaviour of the injected CO₂ and verify borehole integrity (CO₂ containment) across the caprock interval. The standard suite of 'open hole' downhole geophysical logs includes formation resistivity, neutron porosity, density, sonic velocity, gamma ray, self-potential and temperature. More specialized logging tools include various fracture identification, imaging tools and nuclear magnetic resonance tools.*

- The IEAGHG tool rating of this technology is high (44 %) and it is strongly recommended for "Processes" and "Wellbores" aims of monitoring. The methods are also recommended by the DOE Best Practices as "Wireline Deployed Well Logging Tools" and by the Guidance Document 2 as "Well Logging" for parameters group "Plume" monitoring. The technology fulfils the conditions defined by point 1.3., letters b) and c) of the Annex to the Storage Act.
- A good-quality dataset of well logs from Zar-3 is available and can serve as baseline. The applicability of well logging for monitoring is also supported by the fact that there are open hole intervals available in most of the existing wells (see Chapter 5). It is suggested to analyse the existing data in detail to draw more detailed recommendations for selection of concrete logging methods for the Site Monitoring Plan.
- In addition to the “classical” logging methods described above, it is also suggested to consider utilisation of the pulsed neutron capture (PNC) logging. The method has brought interesting results for monitoring and modelling of CO₂ behaviour in carbonates at the Niagaran pinnacle reefs (Conner et al., 2017). It may be useful for the Zar-3 site as it can distinguish relatively small amounts of injected CO₂.

3) Tracers

- Technology characterization according to the IEAGHG tool: *Tracers are fluids with a distinct chemical property that provide a unique fingerprint for the injected CO₂. A range of natural and artificial tracers are available to provide information about the transport and dispersion of the injected CO₂. There are two main objectives for using tracers for CO₂ storage site monitoring:*
 - a) To assess and confirm the migration and behaviour of CO₂ in the reservoir; this can be useful for "plume tracking", understanding fluid pathways and also to help determine the fate of the CO₂ in the reservoir (mineral reactions, residual trapping, dissolution etc). This relies on one or more monitoring boreholes (e.g. production wells in a depleted hydrocarbon reservoir).*
 - b) To aid in the detection or verification of any leakage from the storage reservoir (e.g. through over- / underburden fluid sampling or more often, surface assurance monitoring). It may be possible to estimate the volume and the flow rate of CO₂ leakage if the volume and flow rate of tracer leakage can be measured, assuming even mixing of the tracer with the CO₂ plume and no tracer-CO₂ partitioning (which may not be the case).*

In both cases, the tracer allows the injected CO₂ to be distinguished from other "background" sources of CO₂ and may potentially distinguish between CO₂ originating from adjacent storage sites. This will become important if it proves necessary to refute leakage allegations.

- The IEAGHG tool rating of this technology is high (44 %) and it is "definitely applicable" for "Detect" and "Wellbores" aims of monitoring. The method is also recommended by the DOE Best Practices as "Atmospheric Tracers" and by the Guidance Document 2 as "Tracers" for "Plume" parameters group of monitoring. This technology fulfils the conditions defined by point 1.3., letters a) and c) of the Annex to the Storage Act.
- Selection of the most suitable tracer(s) for monitoring of CO₂ storage at Zar-3 must be based on the results of site characterisation, in particular on the outcomes of WP5 “Geochemistry of rocks and fluids” and WP6 “Risks analysis”.

4) Surface seismic - time-lapse 3D seismic and multi-component seismic

- Technologies characterization according to the IEAGHG tool: *3D surface seismic is a sophisticated deep echo-sounding technique utilising multiple seismic sources and receivers to produce full volumetric images of subsurface structure in both reservoir and overburden. A key application of 3D surface seismic for monitoring purposes is in time-lapse (4D) mode, in which a number of repeat surveys are acquired, enabling changes in fluid distribution to be mapped through time. Multi-component surface seismic uses both compressive and shear waves to obtain a more complete characterisation of the subsurface, including improved imaging beneath gas accumulations and improved discrimination of fluid pressure and saturation changes. It is, however, expensive compared to conventional surface seismic.*
- The IEAGHG tool rating of 3D seismic is high (43 %). According to the IEAGHG tool, these technologies are classified as "probably applicable" up to "definitely applicable", mainly for the "Processes" aim of monitoring. The methods are also recommended by the DOE Best Practices as "Seismic Geophysical Methods" and by the Guidance Document 2 for the "Plume" parameters group of monitoring. These technologies fulfil the conditions defined by point 1.3., letters b) and c) of the Annex to the Storage Act.
- A good quality 3D seismic dataset is available for the Zar-3 site as possible baseline (see Chapter 5), even though the changes in the distribution of reservoir fluids during production would probably require execution of another survey directly before the start of CO₂ injection.
- The experience with efficacy of seismic methods for monitoring of CO₂ storage in carbonate reservoirs is, however, mixed. On the one hand, they have provided good results at the Weyburn and Midale fields (White, 2011), on the other hand they were proven inefficient at the Niagaran pinnacle reefs (Kelley at al., 2020). Since the geological settings at Zar-3 are rather complex, the structure is relatively small (resembling thus rather the Niagaran reefs than the large Weyburn and Midale fields) and the CO₂ amount to be stored is quite limited, it is uncertain if seismic methods will be able to detect the relatively small changes in physical properties of the reservoir to be caused by CO₂ injection. It is therefore recommended to perform a detailed feasibility study that would assess the applicability of seismic methods for monitoring purposes at Zar-3. The study should cover both surface 3D seismic and borehole seismic techniques (see point 6 below).
- 3D seismic, 4D seismic and multi-component seismic are very expensive technologies and their inclusion in the Site Monitoring Plan must be carefully considered, based on the results of the above-mentioned feasibility study, as well as a cost/benefit analysis. From this point of view, the application of the costly multi-component seismic is rather questionable.

5) Deep fluid chemistry

- Technology characterization according to the IEAGHG tool: *Changes in deep fluid chemistry can provide valuable insights into CO₂ plume movement, CO₂ solution into pore waters, fluid-rock interactions and well integrity. In particular, long-term borehole monitoring of in situ pH can play an important role in site monitoring. The pH of formation waters is an important geochemical*

parameter in the context of CO₂ storage, since it is indicative of the proportion of CO₂ dissolving into the formation water and can provide insights into the nature of fluid-rock interactions, including mineral trapping. It is also a potential early indicator of CO₂ migration into the overburden.

- The IEAGHG tool rating of this technology is 24 %, it is classified by mark 2, i.e. "probably applicable", mainly for "Processes" and "Calibrate" aims of monitoring. The technology is also recommended by the DOE Best Practices as "Wellbore-based Fluid Monitoring Tools" and by the Guidance Document 2 as "Downhole fluid chemistry" for the group of monitoring parameters "Environmental". This technology fulfils the conditions defined by point 1.3, letters a), b) and c) of the Annex to the Storage Act.
- Baseline data from Zar-3 field are available.

6) Borehole seismic

- Technology characterization according to the IEAGHG tool: *Borehole seismic techniques include cross-hole seismic, vertical seismic profiling (VSP) and distributed acoustic sensing (DAS). The cross-hole seismic technique measures velocity and attenuation characteristics along a 2D profile between wells. VSP is a borehole seismic method where seismic receivers are placed in a wellbore and the seismic source is located on the ground surface. The advantage of VSP over cross-hole seismic is that detailed, high resolution velocity and reflection images of the subsurface can be acquired while providing more freedom in imaging direction. DAS surveys use a similar source and acquisition geometry to VSP surveys, however, the receiver is a fibre-optic cable installed between the casing and borehole wall¹⁴.*
- The IEAGHG tool rating of this technology is 19 %, it is classified by mark 1.3, i.e. "possibly applicable". The technology is also recommended by the DOE Best Practices as "Seismic Geophysical Methods - VSP, crosswell" and by the Guidance Document 2 as "Seismic - VSP and Cross-Hole Seismic Survey" for the group of monitored parameters "Plume". These technologies fulfil the conditions defined by point 1.3, letters b) and c) of Annex to Storage Act.
- Time-lapse Vertical Seismic Profiling, cross-hole seismic and DAS-VSP survey were tested at the Niagaran carbonate reefs but only cross-hole seismic has brought useful results (Kelley et al., 2020). Possible application of borehole seismic methods at Zar-3 should be based – similarly to surface seismic – on the results of a feasibility study that would assess the applicability of all seismic methods on the site in general.

7) Microseismic monitoring

- Technology characterization according to the IEAGHG tool: *Microseismic or passive seismic monitoring involves the detection, measurement and triangulation of low-level seismic events using surface or downhole geophones. Induced seismicity may indicate fracturing of the reservoir due to injection or migration of the injected CO₂.*

¹⁴ The understanding of the term "DAS" has changed in recent years. Nowadays, DAS is understood as a technology that enables continuous, real-time strain measurements along the entire length of a fibre-optic cable. The technique described in the IEAGHG tool would now be marked as DAS-VSP.

- The IEAGHG tool rating of this technology is 12 %, it is classified by mark 1.3, i.e. "possibly applicable". The technology is also recommended by the DOE Best Practices as " Seismic Geophysical Methods - Passive seismic methods" and by the Guidance Document 2 as "Seismic - Microseismic survey (Passive)" for groups of monitored parameters "Plume" and "Pathway". This technology fulfils the conditions defined by point 1.3, letters b) and c) of the Annex to the Storage Act.
- Microseismic monitoring has become an integral part of monitoring plans at many onshore CO₂ storage sites in the last years. In addition to the achievement of the monitoring targets described above, it is important for public acceptance of CO₂ storage projects. Continuous recording of microseismic events helps assuring the regulators and local communities living in the neighbourhoods of storage sites that any possible tremors possibly induced by CO₂ storage are under control. This has been proven, e.g., in case of the Weyburn-Midale project (Jenkins et al., 2015).
- The detailed methodology of microseismic monitoring is always site-specific. For Zar-3, a baseline survey campaign has been planned in CO₂-SPICER. Its results will determine the methodology that will be prepared for the Site Monitoring Plan.

8) **Surface-atmospheric gas flux and Soil gas concentration** (Atmogeochimistry)

- Technology characterization according to the IEAGHG tool: *Measuring the rate of CO₂ flux from the ground surface to the atmosphere may be important in identifying leakage and quantifying the mass of CO₂ leaking from a storage site for use in emissions trading programs. Good baseline data are fundamental in accounting for natural background variations in CO₂ flux. A variety of relatively mature techniques are available for monitoring the composition of soil gas that could be applied if a leak to the atmosphere was suspected. Measurements can be made using either an accumulation chamber of known size placed directly onto the soil, or an eddy covariance tower combining an infra-red gas analyser to measure CO₂ concentration with a sensitive sonic anemometer that records wind speed and direction.*
- The IEAGHG tool rating of this technologies is 8 %, they are classified by mark 1.3, i.e. "possibly applicable". The technologies are also recommended by the DOE Best Practices as "Geochemical Monitoring in the Soil and Vadose Zone" in combination with "Tracers" and by the Guidance Document 2 as "Soil and Vadose Zone Gas Monitoring" for the group of monitored parameters "Environmental". This technology fulfils the conditions defined by point 1.3., letter a) of the Annex to the Storage Act. In addition, this type of monitoring is important for regulators and local communities to demonstrate that the site is not leaking.
- Atmogeochimical baseline survey has been planned at Zar-3 in the framework of CO₂-SPICER. Its results will determine the detailed monitoring methodology to be prepared for the Site Monitoring Plan.

9) **Geochemical Monitoring of Shallow Groundwater**

- Technology characterization according to the DOE Best Practices: *Geochemical sampling of shallow groundwater above CO₂ storage reservoir to demonstrate isolation of the reservoir from drinking water accumulation. Chemical analyses*

may include pH, alkalinity, electrical conductivity, major and minor elements, dissolved gasses, tracers, and many other parameters. Sensor probes/meters, as well as titration test kits, can be used to test/ sample in the field. Mature technology, samples are collected with shallow monitoring wells. Sensors may be inserted into the aquifer.

- The IEAGHG tool rating for the technology, called here "Shallow Subsurface Geochemistry", is only 5 % but the DOE Best Practices, considers this technology very important (the second "place" in the group "Near-surface Monitoring"). The "Ground-water Monitoring" is recommended also by the Guidance Document 2 for the group of monitored parameters "Environmental". This technology fulfils the conditions defined by point 1.3., letter a) of the Annex to the Storage Act. Together with atmogeochemical monitoring (see point 8 above), this technique is important for regulators and local communities to demonstrate zero leakage from the site.

10) Borehole gravity measurements

- Technology characterization according to the DOE Best Practices: *Use of gravity measurements to monitor changes in density of fluid resulting from injection of CO₂, which is substituted for brine or other reservoir fluids. Gravity measurement provides a direct assessment of the parameter wanted, mass of CO₂, unlike all other measures, which are proxies and must be converted by modelling into an estimate of mass. Technology is still maturing. Limited detection and resolution unless gravimeters are located just above reservoir (i.e. in a well), which significantly increases cost. Noise and gravity variations (tides, drift) need to be eliminated to interpret gravity anomalies due to CO₂.*
- The IEAGHG tool rating of the technology, called here "Borehole gravimetry", is only 4 %; it is, however, recommended by the DOE Best Practices and by the Guidance Document 2 as "Time-lapse Gravity" and "Well Gravimetry" for the group of monitored parameters "Plume". The technology fulfils the conditions defined by point 1.3., letter b) of the Annex to the Storage Act.
- Borehole gravimetry was successfully applied in monitoring of the Niagaran carbonate reefs (Gupta et al., 2017, Kelley et al., 2020).
- Borehole gravimetry is still an immature technology and the number of contractors capable of delivering the instrumentation and/or survey as a service is limited worldwide. It is recommended for consideration at Zar-3, especially in case seismic is not found capable of tracking the CO₂ plume. In any case, its deployment should be justified by positive modelling results prior to the survey. A cost/benefit analysis is strongly recommended as well.

The recommendations of monitoring technologies (methods, techniques) to be used at Zar-3, stated above in points 1) - 10), are summarized in the applicability matrix in Tab. 6-1. The matrix also includes mandatory monitoring technologies (wellhead pressure, temperature, CO₂ flow and composition measurements) according to the Storage Act Annex, point 1.2. Applicability of each technology with respect to the group of monitoring parameters according to the Guidance Document 2 is indicated.

Tab. 6-1: Applicability matrix of monitoring methods for Zar-3 (number of crosses: 5 = mandatory, 4 = strongly recommended, 3 = definitely applicable, 2 = probably applicable)

	Annex 1.2. Operational	Annex 1.3. a) Environmental	Annex 1.3. b) Plume	Annex 1.3. c) Pathway
Wellhead pressure and temperature measurements	+++++ (mandatory)			
Wellhead flow metering & composition	+++++ (mandatory)			
Downhole pressure and temperature measurements	+++++ (mandatory)		++++	++++
Geophysical logs (well logging)			++++	++++
Tracers		+++	++	+++
Surface seismic (3D, multi-component seismic)		+ to be clarified	+++ to be clarified	+++ to be clarified
Deep (Downhole) fluid chemistry		++	++	++
Borehole seismic (VSP, cross-hole)			+++ to be clarified	++ to be clarified
Microseismic monitoring			+++	+++
Atmogeochimistry		++++		
Borehole gravimetry			+++ to be clarified	++ to be clarified

7 CONCLUSIONS

Result R7.4 provides a detailed assessment of applicability of various monitoring methods and techniques at the Zar-3 site. Based on international knowledge and experiences with CO₂ injection and storage in carbonates, it defines a set of the most suitable methods to comply with the regulatory requirements and the overall goal to confirm and verify safe geological storage of CO₂.

For some of the recommended methods – in particular for atmogeochemical, seismological and shallow groundwater monitoring – the applicability, and especially the detailed, site-specific methodology, need to be tested and verified by on-site baseline field surveys that will be performed later during the project within Tasks 7.2 – 7.5. The methodology for application of tracers needs to be based on results of geochemical site characterisation. The uncertainties related to the usability of seismic methods for tracking the CO₂ plume need to be handled by a specialized study, involving forward modelling and simulations. A similar procedure is recommended for borehole gravimetry.

Result R7.4 represents a fundamental input in the preparation of the Site Monitoring Plan – one of the principal project outcomes, to be delivered in Task T7.6 at the end of the project. For this, it needs to be combined with the above-mentioned outcomes of baseline field monitoring, results of the special feasibility study targeted at the applicability of seismic monitoring methods and assessments of applicability of tracers and borehole gravity surveys.

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